

Adopting Cryptocurrency in Nigeria: Tax, Legal and Financial Implications

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Abstract: *Cryptocurrency, a digital finance innovation enabled by Blockchain technology, is altering payment methods and the function of money in the present financial environment. Bitcoin, the most prominent cryptocurrency, has gone through numerous names, including digital currency, digital cash, virtual currency, electronic currency, and cryptocurrency. Bitcoin was widely assumed to be the creation of an anonymous inventor with the pseudonymous moniker Nakamoto. However, before the release of Nakamoto's white paper in 2008, there had been earlier proposals by other writers regarding the efficient role that the market could play in the creation and control of money rather than leaving it in the hands of the government and the banking system. Regardless of the regulatory issues offered by bitcoin technology, it has legitimate uses, Crypto enhances financial inclusion; it makes international remittances cheaper and faster; and it facilitates international trade, particularly at the micro-level. The financial consequences have been discovered to include an absence of central authority, tax evasion, terrorism financing, money laundering, and cyber blackmail. Following several fraud incidents and reviews, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) declared on February 5, 2021, through banks and other financial institutions, that dealing in cryptocurrency and enabling its exchange is illegal. This was ostensibly done to safeguard the integrity of the Nigerian financial system.*

Keywords: Blockchain, Currency law, Cryptocurrency, Financial inclusion, Money, Taxation

Introduction

Discussions on cryptocurrencies are currently a point of debate in global banking, economic, finance, legal, and technological conferences, as well as institutional and academic research, with an emphasis on what and how nations and legislators should respond to this new world-shaking technology.¹ Currency is recognised as a unit of account, a store of value, and a medium of exchange.

Until the emergence of computers, paper money was the primary medium of exchange. Although paper as a means for capturing accounting information has not been eliminated with the arrival of computers, the majority of accounting procedures were automated to capitalise on the plethora of

¹ M. Bech and R. Garratt, Central bank cryptocurrencies. *BIS Quarterly Review*, 55-70, 2017.

benefits afforded by the usage of computers.² Paper was progressively supplanted by computer spreadsheets and other application software, which are still in use today. Many researchers regard the transition from paper to computer spreadsheets and other application software as spanning the third industrial revolution (digitisation).

The world has become a global village since the development of the internet and mobile telephone technology, as communication from one region of the world to the other is becoming simple and more efficient³, The ease of connection across national boundaries is made possible by technological breakthroughs has considerably improved international trade. Business transactions can now be completed between people that live on opposite sides of the globe without the need for personal interaction. As a result, the speed of online transactions appears to have overtaken the traditional payment system over time, making it less efficient.

Cryptocurrency, a digital finance innovation enabled by Blockchain technology, is altering payment methods and the function of money in the present financial environment.⁴ The influence of technology innovation is far-reaching, as it affects the entire financial services market and alters the landscape for intermediation. Individuals, corporations, and the economy as a whole stand to benefit from these improvements, such as cheaper and speedier payments.⁵ However, new regulatory risks, particularly jurisdictional concerns, such as the fight against money laundering, terrorist funding, and tax evasion, to name a few, are being developed. While some nations have explicitly banned virtual money, others are enacting laws to limit the risks and maximise the benefits it provides. The Nigerian government, through its regulatory agencies, has issued repeated cautions against investing in trading cryptocurrency, particularly considering the risk of loss of investment; nonetheless, there is presently no global legal framework for the operation of crypto.

So yet, economic research has provided little insight into the economic significance of cryptocurrencies. Most existing cryptocurrency models are created by computer scientists who are primarily concerned with the practicality and security of these systems. Important difficulties, such as the incentives for players to cheat and the endogenous nature of some essential variables, such as the true worth of a cryptocurrency in trade, have largely gone unnoticed. Such concerns, however, are critical for comprehending the ideal design and, as a result, the economic worth of cryptocurrencies as a payment method.⁶

Bitcoin, for example, is not controlled by any Central Bank. It does, however, have two levels of governance: the algorithm and open-source governance. Furthermore, "miners" who are involved

² J. K. Nkuah, A. K. Frederick and K. Asamoah, "The correlation between accounting systems of small and micro enterprises and tax revenue assessment in Ghana". *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 2 no. 1, 1-12, 2015

³ D. Bryans, "Bitcoin and money laundering: mining for an effective solution". *Indiana Law Journal*, 89, 441-472, 2014.

⁴ FATF. "Virtual currencies: Key definitions and potential AML/CFT Risks. <http://fatfgafi.org/media/fatf/documents/reports/Virtual-currency-key-definitions-and-potential-aml-cft-risks.pdf> (2015). (Accessed May 27, 2023).

⁵ C. E. Onyeke, 2020.

⁶ J. Chiu and T. V. Koepl, "The economics of cryptocurrencies: Bitcoin and beyond". A paper supported by SSHRC Insight Grant 435-2014-141, 1-59, 2018.

in the process of producing bitcoin safeguard the process's sanctity.⁷ Since the inception of Bitcoin in 2009, several opponents have labelled cryptocurrencies as fraudulent or blatant speculative bubbles. More sophisticated viewpoints contend that such currencies exist solely to encourage payments for unlawful activity or to waste resources. However, advocates argue that because these new currencies are built on cryptographic principles to maintain security, they can facilitate payments without the need for a third party to control the currency or payment instrument, possibly for its benefit.⁸ This sparked enthusiasm and a desire to learn more about the benefits and financial repercussions of cryptocurrencies on the Nigerian economy.

Blockchain Technology

Blockchain is a decentralised digital ledger system that allows valid and highly secure transactions to take place over a point-to-point network. It was invented in 2008 by an unidentified individual behind the online cash currency Bitcoin, using the pseudonym Satoshi Nakamoto, and first used in 2009 as a technology to use Bitcoins. Since then, blockchain has grown in popularity and utility across a wide range of industries.

Blockchain is primarily a distributed database that is open source, allowing anybody to update the underlying code and monitor the status of an operation. It is a peer-to-peer network with a vast worldwide database that works on trillions of machines. It does not necessitate the use of any controlling intermediaries to confirm transactions.⁹ The reach of blockchain technology can dismantle critical impediments to efficiency, commitment, and scale. It could record any structured data from beginning to end.

Blockchain is a protocol—a way of doing things—rather than a particular technology. In contrast to the internet, where data is shared, ownership in blockchain can be transferred from one party to another. For a variety of reasons, blockchain is the desired model. It may, for example, eliminate the need to reconcile various ledgers in a Market with multiple transacting players. The ledger is spread among users, which eliminates downtime and eliminates the need of paying a central authority to keep the ledger accurate.¹⁰

Cryptocurrencies: A Robust Discussion

There is no universally accepted definition of the term "cryptocurrency." However, the European Union described it as "a digital representation of value that is not issued or guaranteed by a central bank or a public authority, is not necessarily attached to a legally established currency, does not have the legal status of currency or money, but is accepted as a means of exchange by natural or legal persons, and can be transferred, stored, and traded electronically".¹¹ Cryptocurrencies are

⁷ T. T. Siyanbola, S. I., Audu A. R., Adediran and A. Agbaje, "Cryptocurrency and the Nigerian Economy". African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research, 4(3), 180-193, 2021.

⁸ See J. Chiu and T. V. Koepl, 2018.

⁹ E. C. Okpalaojiego, "Effects and implications of crypto currency ban on Nigerian economy". Academic Journal of Current Research, 8 no. 4, 23-33, 2021.

¹⁰ S. Onoja, "Blockchain Technologies and Tax Implications of Cryptocurrencies, 2022.

¹¹ European Union, "Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive (EU). 2015/849 on the prevention of the use of the financial system for the purposes of money laundering or terrorist financing.

peer-to-peer (P2P) trading and settlement networks that use cryptographic verification to verify transactions and create consensus about network connections without relying on a trusted third-party, such as a bank or financial institution. It serves as a type of 'digital cash,' allowing direct transactions between two parties in the same way that two people could exchange conventional fiat currency, but without the same constraints of place and distance.

Cryptocurrencies are private, digital, de-nationalised, unreserved, floating rate, convertible monies. Bitcoin, the most prominent cryptocurrency, has gone through numerous names, including digital cash, digital currency, electronic cash, virtual money, and cryptocurrency.¹² Bitcoin was widely assumed to be the work of an anonymous inventor with the pseudonymous name Nakamoto. However, before the release of Nakamoto's white paper in 2008, there had been earlier proposals by other writers addressing the efficient role the market should play in the creation and control of money rather than leaving it in the hands of the government and the financial system.¹³

Bitcoin was the first cryptocurrency, launched in 2009, and represented a substantial advancement over previous attempts to construct digital cash systems, which had always needed the presence of a central issuing party to oversee network operations and mint new coins. Bitcoin's origins may be traced back to the libertarian leanings of the cryptographer community known as 'cypherpunks,' who believed that the development of decentralised, alternative payment systems free of government or bank control was critical to the development of true financial independence.¹⁴ Satoshi Nakamoto, the originator of Bitcoin, proposed that the development of a peer-to-peer payments system would reduce dependence on the highly intermediated mainstream financial system, which includes third parties such as financial institutions and credit card issuers that can charge fees and profit from inefficiencies.

Although Bitcoin was the first-known cryptocurrency, there have been several other virtual currencies since the introduction of Bitcoin, including Litecoin (LTC), Ethereum (ETH), Neo, Iota, Dash, Qtum, Monero, Ripple (XRP), Bitcoin Cash, Peercoin, anoncoin, Namecoin, Quackcoin, and Zerocoin, among others. They also use technology that is like Bitcoin.¹⁵

The usage of Bitcoin as a basic money account aims to provide everyone with the right to a verifiable digital identity, and there are many predictions about its future. First, the lack of central control by any government or administrator is a major source of concern for governments on all continents. The recurring record of illegal transactions, financing of terrorists' activities, the fear of a sudden crash of the entire system, and the difficulty of defining the coin are just a few of the reasons why most countries constantly warn their citizens against investing in it. At the same time,

<http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?type=TA&language=EN&reference=P8-TA-2018-0178>
(Accessed May 25, 2023).

¹² O. J. Mandeng, "Cryptocurrencies, monetary stability and regulation: Germany's nineteenth century private banks of issue. Ousmène Jacques Mandeng Lse Institute of Global Affairs. 2018..

¹³ M. N. Rothbard, "What has government done to our money?" Auburn, AL: Ludwig von Mises Institute. Security and Exchange Commission. www.sec.gov/spotlight/enf-actions-ponzi (Accessed June 15, 2023).

¹⁴ L. Jameson, "Bitcoin and the Rise of the Cypherpunks. CoinDesk". <https://www.coindesk.com/the-rise-of-the-cypherpunks/> (Accessed January 5, 2022)

¹⁵ M. K Salawu and T. Moloi, "Benefits of legislating cryptocurrencies: Perception of Nigerian professional accountants". *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 22 no 6, 1-17, 2018.

it offers significant and appealing potential as well as huge profits to investors. An earlier study¹⁶ had adequately outlined the cryptocurrency strategy, its ideal characteristics, and the problems that would characterise the currency in its early stages. The authors went on to say that its characteristics would include, among other things, efficient global economies, and societies, on the one hand, greater anti-competitive behaviour, exclusion and inequality, economic volatility, criminal activity, and weakened macroeconomic policy on the other.

Before the advent of cryptocurrency, all currencies were centrally administered and regulated by the central bank of each country¹⁷, but this is no longer the case with Bitcoin. At the time, bitcoin technology cannot distinguish between the rightful owner of an account and a successful attacker because the crypto private key is accessible to attackers who can easily calculate the rightful owner's account address and obtain immediate control. Worse, the lawful owners cannot undo the transactions previously completed by the crypto attacker, even with the assistance of a law court.¹⁸

New cryptocurrencies appear daily, with early adopters making millions while other investors lose money. The market appears to be in disarray, but that does not change the fact that cryptocurrencies are here to stay. Even though the institutional currency is utilised as a medium of exchange in some transactions. This does not imply that Bitcoin will be regulated like property in all aspects and all transactions. Investors who are heavily invested in cryptocurrencies, banks, and governments are realising that this innovation has the potential to erode their influence.¹⁹

According to a 2017 study conducted by Cambridge University academics, the number of individual bitcoin users ranges between three and six million, with up to 11.5 million cryptocurrency wallets in active use.²⁰ A cryptocurrency wallet represents a user's 'private keys,' which are essentially passwords used to sign transactions connected with the user's public bitcoin addresses on the blockchain. The individual who has access to the private keys is the true owner of the related coin. Private keys can be stored in memory or written down. However, bitcoin users prioritise the security of their private keys because the theft or loss of those keys results in the user losing access to their cryptocurrency.

Challenges of Cryptocurrency

Certain characteristics of cryptocurrency may be appealing to users in terms of adoption. At the same time, several of the characteristics present difficulties for investors, users, and lawmakers. This paper examines six of these qualities that are thought to be most relevant to the research aims. The absence of central authority; tax evasion; terrorism financing; money laundering; and cyber blackmail are among them.

¹⁶ R. Miller, W. Michalski and B. Stevens, "The future of money. Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development". OECD Publication, 2002.

¹⁷ See O. J. Mandeng, 2018.

¹⁸ J. Lansky, "Possible state approaches to Cryptocurrencies". Journal of Systems Integration, 9 no. 1, 19-31. (2018)

¹⁹ L. D. Iyoyojie, O. J. Edeh, U. Erinne and C. Umezurike, "Cryptocurrency: The search for a legal framework as a world currency". International Journal of Business & Law Research, 9 no. 3, 15-25, 2021.

²⁰ H. Garrick, and R. Michael, Global Cryptocurrency Benchmarking Study, Cambridge Centre for Alternative Finance and University of Cambridge Judge Business School, 2017.

Absence of Central Authority: There is no single authority or institution specifically in charge of cryptocurrencies administration. All users are autonomous of one another. Although the account information of each participant's transactions is public, there is no agency responsible for the supervision of its activities.²¹ Cryptocurrency account maintenance incorporates a self-regulating process comparable to the internal control mechanisms found in client-oriented organisations.²² Transactions are sequentially dependent on one another since the previous block's cryptographic hash is contained in the succeeding block. It was created by an anonymous developer(s) and is used by an anonymous user. Because there is no traceable central administrator in charge of Bitcoin's functionality, its difficulties include constraints of law enforcement agencies identifying, tracing, and holding any individual or business liable for investigative purposes. This Bitcoin feature appears to be exceedingly risky for investors in the event of any unforeseen situations.

Tax Evasion: Bitcoin (and other cryptocurrencies) provide tax evaders with a fresh edge that traditional tax havens do not. This is because the operation of Bitcoin is not reliant on the presence of financial middlemen such as banks.²³ A service provider, for example, might hypothetically accept Bitcoin payments for real-world services. Given that the service provider is not needed to identify herself when creating her online Bitcoin wallet, tracing the earnings accumulated in this wallet back to the service provider would be extremely difficult. Such money is taxable in most (if not all) jurisdictions throughout the world; but, unless the service provider voluntarily declares it, tax authorities are unlikely to be aware of it.

Terrorism Financing: Terrorism is heavily reliant on finance, ranging from the purchase of firearms to domain names and leaflets. Terrorist organisations have always used a range of methods to launder and finance their terrorist activities. Terrorists use a variety of methods in their operations. The two of the most prevalent techniques are Hawala networks (underground banking) and traditional international banking. Terrorists use this mechanism to transfer money from one location to another. Terrorists who are sending and receiving finances may encounter constraints that limit their scope.²⁴ Cryptocurrency appears to provide superior alternatives, or at least the opportunity to do so. This is due to the system's design, which includes no names or other customer identification tied to addresses that serve as accounts, and the lack of a central server or service provider. Again, the Bitcoin protocol does not demand or provide participant identification and verification, nor does it generate historical records of transactions that are necessarily related to real-world identities.²⁵

²¹ See M. K Salawu and T. Moloi, 2018.

²² International Public Accountants (IPA) "Classifying cryptocurrencies". <http://www.pubacct.org.au/blog/classifying> (Accessed June 28, 2023)

²³ See FAFT, 2015.

²⁴ See. C. E. Onyeke, 2020.

²⁵ M. Staples, S. Chen, S. Falamanski, A. Ponomarev, P. Rimba, A. P., Tran, I. Weber, X, Xu and J Zhu, "Risks and opportunities for systems using blockchain and smart contracts". Canberra. Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, 2017.

Money Laundry: Traditionally, money mules, offshore accounts, or expensive things such as art, mansions, boats, or a mix of those have been used to enable the laundering of crime money.²⁶ Alternative payment systems, such as Western Union and Perfect Money, are said to play an important role in money laundering schemes. Prepaid credit cards, gift certificates, and other easily exchangeable non-traditional value goods are also frequently related to crime money laundering.²⁷ Today, so-called innovative payment channels are playing a larger role in actual money laundering activities. There is a noticeable shift in which criminals are increasingly using cryptocurrencies to cash out their proceeds.

Bitcoin has the advantage of allowing any user, including money launderers, to move funds at near-instantaneous speed for little or no cost, with quite low entry barriers, while remaining virtually untraceable without the need for a public paper trail.²⁸ Users' ability to exchange bitcoins directly for other currencies, transfer through an infinite number of distinct Bitcoin addresses for obfuscation, and trade for tangible goods with other users further thwarts AML efforts. Essentially, Bitcoin and similar virtual currencies could allow money launderers to move illicit monies more quickly, cheaply, and surreptitiously than ever before.

Cyber Blackmail: In this sense, it is successful blackmail, also known as cyber-extortion, which has been described as a frightening demand made without justification. Cyber-extortion appears to have existed before the establishment of Bitcoin, but its creation has seen an exponential increase in cyber-extortion. The use of ransomware is an unusual type of cyber-extortion. Ransomware is software that encrypts data on a host smartphone or computer to extract a ransom payment in exchange for the decryption key. Ransomware is used for extortion by encrypting the victim's digital property for a fee. The majority of ransomware cyber-extortionists favour Bitcoin as their preferred 'banking' method.²⁹

Benefits of Legislating Cryptocurrencies

Despite the regulatory risks posed by cryptocurrency technology, it has legitimate uses. It improves financial inclusion; it is cheaper and faster in international remittances; and it aids international trade, especially at the micro-level.

Financial Inclusion: It is feasible to think of Bitcoin as a form of decentralised bank. A person can receive a public key that represents their account on the global system if they have a personal computer or a mobile phone that can be used to install a Bitcoin wallet. This, in turn, resembles a sort of bank account where you can save money. In the context of a country with a lack of banking infrastructure and a reliance on cash, such technology may theoretically be a safer method to retain money and a more convenient way to transmit money in regular transactions.³⁰ Rather than being

²⁶ A. Freeman, "Bitcoin: The Ultimate Offshore Bank Account? Economics and liberty: <http://economicsandliberty.wordpress.com/2011/08/23/bitcoin-the-ultimate-offshore-bankaccount/> (Accessed January .2023).

²⁷ World Bank. "World bank financial inclusion: Overview". <http://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/financialinclusion/overview> (Accessed June 29, 2023).

²⁸ L. Ijaodola, "Cryptocurrency: Money laundering implications in Nigeria". G. Elias & Co. 1-5 (2021)

²⁹ L. D. Iyoyojie, O. J. Edeh, U. Erinne and C. Umezurike, "Cryptocurrency: The search for a legal framework as a world currency". International Journal of Business & Law Research, 9 no. 3: (2021): 15-25.

³⁰ See. C. E. Onyeke, 2020.

limited to remittance systems, Bitcoin might serve as a foundation for ordinary local payments in insecure, informal situations. In this way, Bitcoin has the potential to supplement or compete with mobile banking apps.

International Remittances: Remittances into international accounts necessitate several procedures and norms. Bitcoin could conceivably be used to circumvent such banks and build an alternative remittance system. Individually, remittances are low-value payments. Nonetheless, they account for up to 10% of GDP in some underdeveloped nations (27% in Tonga and 20% in Samoa).³¹ As a result, high remittance costs have significant repercussions on these countries' socioeconomic progress. It costs less than or equals 2% using Bitcoin. In 2018, remittances into Nigeria totalled \$24.3 billion (6.1% of GDP). As a result, if the rate of transfers to Vanuatu and Samoa from Australia is used, Nigeria might save up to 14.6% and 12.3% in remittance costs, respectively.³² Whereas Western Union transfers might take anything from an hour to five days, Bitcoin transfers are instant.³³

International Commerce: Bitcoin has the potential to assist small-scale international trade as well. Local merchants in the developing world may have difficulty accessing international payment networks to sell their items abroad. A rural crafts cooperative in Nigeria, for example, may struggle to put up a website with an integrated credit card payments system, but obtaining a Bitcoin address may allow them to sell products in return for Bitcoin tokens, avoiding regular e-commerce platforms (which often requires having to set up a merchant account with a formal bank). This could be advantageous if a market existed to exchange such bitcoins obtained in a trade back into a useable local currency. Similarly, a small-scale non-governmental group can easily set up an account to accept Bitcoin tokens as donations.³⁴

Currency Laws and the Legality of Cryptocurrencies in Nigeria

According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Act 2007, the CBN is empowered to issue legal tender currency in Nigeria. The CBN 2007 Act also states that the naira, which is divisible into 100 kobo, is the unit of currency in Nigeria.³⁵ The CBN shall have sole authority over the issuance of currency notes and coins throughout Nigeria, and neither the Federal Government nor any State or Local Government, or any other person or authority, shall issue currency notes, banknotes, coins, or any documents or tokens payable to bearer on demand, being documents or tokens likely to pass as legal tender. The CBN is also responsible for determining the naira's exchange rate with other fiat currencies around the world, as well as arranging for the printing of currency notes and coin minting. The CBN's currency notes and coins are legal tenders in Nigeria at their face value for payment of any amount.

³¹ World Bank. "World bank financial inclusion: Overview".

³² NDIC "Press Release. <https://ndic.gov.ng/ndic-urges-caution-on-adoption-of-crypto-currencies/> (Accessed May 23, 2023)

³³ S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: a peer-to-peer electronic cash system". Consulted, 1-9, <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf> (Accessed June 25, 2023).

³⁴ See, C, E, Onyeke 2020.

³⁵ See. CBN ACT 2007

The CBN Act, the Decimal Currency Act, and other Nigerian currency legislation are mostly applicable to Nigerian currency. When they mention foreign currency, they appear to be referring to foreign fiat currency. However, one could argue that the Foreign Exchange (Monitoring and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act (the "Forex Act") applies to cryptocurrency. Because the Forex Act defines foreign currency as "any currency other than Nigerian money," this is the case. However, a quick read of the Forex Act reveals that what the Act envisions are foreign fiat currencies.

The preceding is unsurprising. Cryptocurrencies were essentially non-existent at the time these regulations were enacted. They first appeared as decentralised money mechanisms in 2009. Although not contemplated under Nigerian currency regulations, it is debatable that they are not legal tender or acceptable currencies in Nigeria because they have not been issued by the CBN or any other central authority or government in the world. Precise legislation on them is thus desirable to effectively control cryptocurrency as a rising and nearly unavoidable currency for global financial operations.³⁶

The Central Bank of Nigeria issued a circular in January 2017 prohibiting regulated institutions from transacting in virtual currencies in any way. Then, on February 5th, 2021, the Central Bank of Nigeria, through banks and other financial institutions, said that trading in cryptocurrency and facilitating its exchange is forbidden with effect from February 5th, 2021.³⁷ To maintain the integrity of the Nigerian financial system, the circular asks banks and other reporting financial institutions to take the following actions, awaiting substantive regulation or determination by the CBN:

- i. Ensure that they do not use, hold, and /or transact in any way in virtual currencies.
- ii. Ensure that existing customers, that are virtual currency exchangers, have effective AML/CFT controls that enable them to comply with customer identification, verification, and transaction monitoring requirements.
- iii. Where banks or other financial institutions are not satisfied with the controls put in place by the virtual currency exchangers/customers, the relationship should be discontinued immediately, and
- iv. any suspicious transactions by these customers should immediately be reported to the Nigerian Financial Intelligence Unit (NFIU).

In response to the ban, Vice President Yemi Osibanjo³⁸ stated that there is a role for regulation, in which both the monetary authorities and the security and exchange commission would provide a robust regulatory regime that can address the buying and selling of cryptocurrency without killing the goose that could lay the golden egg. He stated that blockchain technology in general, and cryptocurrencies, would threaten traditional banking, especially reserve banking, in ways that we cannot yet understand, and that we must be prepared for that seismic change, which may occur

³⁶ O. A. Abdullateef, *Cryptocurrencies in Nigeria: A legal analysis*. https://www.academia.edu/37770552/cryptocurrencies_in_nigeria_a_legal_analysis (Accessed July 2, 2023)

³⁷ A. A. Adedipe and O. Atanda, (2021). Nigeria prohibition of crypto currency transactions by the central bank of Nigeria. <https://pavestoneslegal.com/prohibition-of-cryptocurrency-transactions-by-the-central-bank-of-nigeria/> (Accessed June 10, 2023)

³⁸ See Yemi Osibajo comments on the CBN ban on cryptocurrencies in Nigeria, 2021.

sooner rather than later. According to Ezekwesili³⁹, the ban on trading and transacting in cryptocurrency makes Nigeria appear unprepared for the new transformation.

Cryptocurrencies and the Nigeria Economy

The emergence of Bitcoin as a virtual currency has caused a ripple effect in the global economy, even in a poor country like Nigeria. As a result of this spread, there has been a lot of discussion on the value of cryptocurrencies on the Nigerian economy, both positive and negative. In comparison, the Nigerian government has completely banned cryptocurrency through government regulators such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), just like Algeria and Morocco Algeria, where there is also a concise ban on trading in Bitcoins, with heavy fines for violations.

All regulated financial institutions were ordered by the central bank to close all cryptocurrency-related accounts. Soon after, the central bank said in mid-2021 that it will launch a trial central bank digital currency in October 2021. The Nigerian central bank dubbed the digital money scheme 'Project Giant.' Given the local circumstances in Nigeria, as well as the widespread interest in cryptocurrencies among economic agents, particularly individuals and businesses, questions have begun to arise about the opportunities and risks of CBDC in Nigeria, how the Nigeria CBDC or the eNaira will be used in Nigeria, whether it will be well-received by citizens, and how it can solve some of the problems associated with paper money in Nigeria.⁴⁰

Monetary Policy: Presently, cryptocurrencies coexist with traditional currencies. The current amounts are minimal and do not pose a threat to the dominance of official money as the primary currency. However, as algorithms develop to limit the volatility of cryptocurrencies, their popularity and use grow. This would result in the currency coexisting with other official currencies. Fernandes-Villa Verde and Sanches (2018) forecast that the cohabitation of the central bank and private money is dependent on the sort of monetary policy followed by the former. Privately issued currencies, for instance, would be utilised if official currencies failed to achieve price stability but would lose their usefulness as a medium of exchange if the central bank legitimately guaranteed the true worth of money balances.⁴¹ The consequences are twofold. First, the cohabitation of government money and cryptocurrencies valued as media of trade is not an impossibility in theory. Second, central banks have the benefit of preventing cryptocurrencies from being valued as a medium of exchange by implementing a certain sort of monetary policy. From this point of view, rather than constituting a threat, the coexistence of government money and cryptocurrencies can be beneficial by acting as a deterrent to central banks. Currency competition has the potential to reduce inflation and prevent the kind of interest rate and price manipulation that overnments have historically been prone to.

³⁹ O. Ezekwesili, Implication of CBN Crypto currency ban. The Cable, Retrieved from <https://www.thecable.ng/how-nigerias-economy-can-benefit-from-cryptocurrency-trading/amp> (Accessed July 3, 2023)

⁴⁰ P. K. Ozili, "Central Bank Digital Currency in Nigeria: Opportunities and Risks". SSRN Electronic Journal, 1-17, 2022

⁴¹ C. G. Ahannaya and A. D. Oshinowo, A. S., Sanni, J. A., Arogundade, and O. J. Ogunwole, "The effect of cryptocurrencies on Nigeria economy." International European Extended Enablement in Science, Engineering & Management (IEEE-SEM), 9 no 3, 8-14, 2021.

Fiscal Policy: Cryptocurrency and fiscal policy can have an unbalanced relationship. In an economy with an underdeveloped financial market, cryptocurrency activity may be difficult to control and, as such, could provide a platform for investors, both individuals, and corporate organisations, to evade tax, leading to a lower income generation for the government relative to the level of activity in the market, which may affect the government's budgetary plans. This circumstance may impede the government's fiscal aims, consequently impacting fiscal macroeconomic objectives. Furthermore, in an economy with a highly developed financial sector, the correct coordination of Bitcoin might result in an increase in income generation through taxation, which would improve the government's fiscal projections. This condition may help to improve the government's fiscal aims, consequently improving fiscal macroeconomic objectives and stabilising the economy.⁴²

Taxation and Cryptocurrencies in Nigeria

Taxation, as an important component of human society, is a holistic representation of the society's shared values, goals, and aspirations. In essence, taxes not only provide income to finance governance, but also ensure wealth redistribution, job creation, inflation reduction, and the moderation of consumption of particular products and services.

The continual transition of human activities from a physically-oriented commercial environment to one driven by technology raises serious and significant difficulties in terms of taxation and tax regimes. Tax administrators are faced with the difficult issue of safeguarding their income base as new technologies emerge. The tax repercussions of using digital currencies are a topic that tax practitioners and academics are particularly interested in.⁴³

Because of international tax information exchange agreements, tax havens have lost their popularity in tax evasion, and cryptocurrencies have become the new preferred currency of investors. However, issues that may arise in cryptocurrency regulations, such as the ineffectiveness of tax proposals resulting from difficulties in precisely determining the values of electronic payments, are not desired to be addressed in the depths of financial markets and can be compared to issues encountered in the delivery of e-services. The challenges encountered in taxation also apply to cryptocurrencies, especially when the online presence of some electronic services is paid out.⁴⁴

Nigerian tax legislation, like that of most other countries, is mainly statutory. The regulation of tax can thus be seen to be wholly *nulla poena sine lege*.⁴⁵ As derived largely from Criminal law,⁴⁶ this phrase states that no one can be convicted for a crime that the laws, at that material time, did/do

⁴² E. G. Peter and S. S. Akadiri, *Cryptocurrency and the Nigerian Economy* 2020.

⁴³ M. A. Adu, "Taxability of cryptocurrency in e-commerce in Nigeria. A long essay submitted to the faculty of law, university of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of bachelor of law (LL.B Hons.) In Common Law

⁴⁴ S. Onoja, "Blockchain Technologies and Tax Implications of Cryptocurrencies

⁴⁵ This is a Latin phrase, meaning: "no penalty without a law".

⁴⁶ A. Mokhtar, 'Nullum Crimen, Nulla Poena Sine Lege: Aspects and Prospects', 26:41, *Statute Law Review*, 2005.

not define as a crime. The application of tax laws thus requires that for a 'thing' to be taxable, the laws must have proclaimed it so. The absence of such legal proscriptions would make such a thing untaxable and promote tax avoidance schemes.

Bitcoins are typically divided into numerous smaller accounts held by the same person, or big sums are transmitted in bulk using multiple wallets. These strategies are frequently used by tax evaders and money launderers to conceal funding sources and destinations.

Even though there is presently no international agreement on how cryptocurrency transactions should be treated for tax reasons, nations such as the United Kingdom and South Africa have imposed taxes on cryptocurrency transactions. Because cryptocurrencies are recognized as chargeable assets for capital gains purposes, both countries impose Capital Gains Tax on their sale. However, there is no special legislation in Nigeria that governs the taxation of virtual currency transactions. Such transactions, therefore, will be subject to the country's current general tax regulations, which means that any income or profit generated from such investments will be taxed in the hands of the investors.⁴⁷

While it is possible to argue that cryptocurrency income, profits, or transactions are taxable, the structure of the virtual currency makes it difficult for authorities to track. The specific tax regulations that will apply to Cryptocurrency will be determined by the final title assigned to it.⁴⁸

Even if governments are hesitant to recognize cryptocurrencies as legal tender, they may consider them appropriate as virtual currency. As a virtual currency, taxes such as Value Added Tax (VAT) and Capital Gains Tax (CGT) will not be recoverable, with the exception of deductions such as commission received by licensed Foreign Exchange business firms.⁴⁹ If cryptocurrency is classified as a virtual asset, it will be subject to a variety of taxes, including VAT, CGT, and others.

There are two reasons for non-compliance with tax requirements regarding the use of cryptocurrencies. The first is that most taxable individuals are unaware that their earnings are taxable. This issue is undoubtedly caused by the lack of unambiguous instruction saying that cryptocurrency users are subject to tax regulations. The other reason is that a significant number of taxable individuals are evading taxes by taking advantage of cryptocurrencies' anonymity. This does not, however, eliminate the propensity of a significant number of taxable individuals to self-assess their tax liability. Similarly, the fact that bitcoins can be used for unlawful activities does not imply that this is a widespread problem. There isn't a single financial system that is impervious to unlawful usage.

⁴⁷ O. Chukwudi, T. Kofoworola, A. Chizotam and E. Timiebi, "The virtual currency regulation review: Nigeria. The Law Reviews. <https://thelawreviews.co.uk/title/the-virtual-currency-regulation-review/nigeria> (Accessed, June 29, 2023)

⁴⁸ A. Guadamuz, and C. Marsden, *Blockchains and Bitcoin: Regulatory Responses to Cryptocurrencies* 20(12), First Monday, 2015

⁴⁹ N. V. Apatov, O. L. Korolev and A. P. Krulikovsky, *Analysis of the Influence of Blockchain Technology on Financial System*. Vol. 10(6), Scientific and Technical Bulletin of St. Petersburg State Polytechnic, 2017

Individuals will be responsible for personal income tax on any profit earned from such transactions as a result of this, while a corporate entity, if medium-sized, will be liable to pay company income tax at the rate of 20 per cent of its taxable income or, if a large company, 30 per cent of its taxable income. However, because of the very nature of cryptocurrency, it will be difficult for the tax authorities to determine and track any gains on such investments.

Conclusion

Every day, new cryptocurrencies arise, with early adopters making millions while other investors lose money. The market appears to be in disarray, but that does not change the fact that cryptocurrencies are here to stay. Financial consequences have been discovered to include a lack of central authority, tax evasion, terrorism financing, money laundering, and cyber blackmail. Despite the regulatory dangers that Bitcoin technology poses, it has valid use. It increases financial inclusion, makes international remittances cheaper and faster, and facilitates international trade, particularly at the micro-level.

Concerning the legality of cryptocurrency in Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has the authority to issue legal tender currency in the country. The "CBN 2007 Act" further specifies that the unit of currency in Nigeria is the naira. The CBN declared on February 5, 2021, through banks and other financial institutions, that dealing in cryptocurrency and facilitating its exchange is forbidden. This was ostensibly done to safeguard the integrity of the Nigerian financial system.